

Fertilizer management—biological N

Blue-green algae (BGA) as a partial N substitute for rainfed lowland rice

R. Singh and S. K. Shrivastava, IGKVV, College of Agriculture, Raipur 492012, Madhya Pradesh, India

BGA has a photo-autotrophic N-fixing system and may be used as partial substitute for N fertilizer in rice.

We conducted a 4-yr field experiment to evaluate the utility of BGA in rainfed lowland rice. JR3-756, Usha, and Asha rice varieties were the test crops.

Soil was red-yellow clay loam with pH 7.00, 1.7% organic matter, CEC 33.8 meq/100 g soil, 0.08% total N, 5 ppm available P (Olsen), and 0.07 meq exchangeable K/100 g soil. P and K were applied basally at 26 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Treatments (see table) were in a random block design with

four replications. N was applied in three splits (25% basal, 50% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation).

Indigenous BGA were not found in any plot. Grain yield and net profit

increased with each incremental level of N alone (see table). Inoculation of 10 kg BGA algal crust/ha gave a grain yield and net profit nearly equivalent to that with 25 kg N/ha. Net profit increased when BGA was supplemented with 25 kg N/ha. □

Utility of BGA inoculation of rainfed lowland rice. Raipur, MP, India.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (tha)					Gross return ^b (US\$)	Cost of treatment (US\$)	Net profit (US\$)
	1978	1979	1980	1981	Mean			
Control (no N)	1.0	3.0	2.7	2.0	2.2	218.00	0.00	218.00
25 kg N/ha as urea	1.2	3.5	3.4	2.5	2.7	265.00	9.25	255.75
50 kg N as urea	1.4	4.4	3.8	2.8	3.1	310.00	18.50	291.50
75 kg N as urea	1.5	4.7	4.2	3.2	3.4	339.00	27.75	311.25
10 kg BGA/ha, algal crust inoculated	1.2	3.6	3.3	2.2	2.6	256.00	0.67	255.33
10 kg BGA/ha, algal crust inoculated + 25 kg N/ha	1.3	3.7	3.5	2.4	2.8	275.00	9.92	265.08
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.6	0.4	0.3				
CV (%)	14	11	7	7				

^aVarieties were JR3-756 for 1978, Ucha for 1979 and 1980, Asha for 1981. ^bRates: rice \$100/t, N \$0.37/kg, BGA \$0.67/10 kg.

Decapitating young *Sesbania rostrata* plants to increase biomass production and nitrogen fixation

S. A. Kulasooriya and I. M. Samarakoon, Botany Department, University of Peradeniya, Peradeniya, and The Institute of Fundamental Studies, Kandy, Sri Lanka

A green manure crop for intensive rice production systems should produce high biomass within a very short fallow. Under optimal conditions, *Sesbania rostrata* has the capacity to produce 5.6 t dry matter with 100 kg N content/ha in 50 d.

Apical dominance in dicotyledonous plants inhibits the growth of axillary buds. Removal of apical dominance would permit more rapid growth of axillary buds, which could result in higher biomass production. Increased stem nodulation has been achieved in *S. rostrata* under laboratory conditions,

by injecting an *Azorhizobial* suspension into the vascular system of the plant.

We examined whether growth and stem nodulation could be improved by decapitating young *sesbania* plants prior to stem inoculation. The experiment was conducted mid-Jun to mid-Aug in the intermediate zone of Sri Lanka (12.5 h daylength). Surface-sterilized *sesbania* seeds were planted

in 3-m² plots, in three rows 10 cm apart, at 20 seeds/row.

Treatments (see table) were in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plots were flooded 35 d after seeding (DAS), when the plants were 30 cm tall. Decapitation and stem inoculation were done 46 DAS, when plants were 50 cm tall.

Stem inoculation was done by

Effect of decapitation and stem inoculation on growth and N₂ fixation in *S. rostrata*.^a

Treatment	Dry weight/plant (g)	Nodule dry weight/plant (g)	ARA (μmol/h)	N yield/plant (mg)
Control - no decapitation, no stem inoculation	4.280 c	0.1196 b	10.8 c	45.3 b
Inoculation without decapitation	6.217 b (45)	0.1898 ab (59)	21.9 b (103)	81.6 ab (80)
Decapitation without inoculation	7.543 b (76)	0.2039 ab (70)	24.7 b (129)	96.9 ab (114)
Decapitation and inoculation	9.287 a (116)	0.3290 a (175)	49.7 a (360)	128.5 a (184)

^a Figures in parentheses are 5% increase over control. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

spraying a suspension of 10^8 *Azorhizobium* cells/ml. Control plants were sprayed with sterile distilled water.

Sesbania plants were harvested at 55 DAS. Fresh and dry weight, nodule number, and nodule biomass/plant

were recorded. Nitrogenase activity was measured by the acetylene reduction technique.

Decapitation without inoculation and inoculation without decapitation increased yield parameters (see table). Decapitation followed by inoculation

produced the highest increase. Decapitating young sesbania plants before stem inoculation could maximize N_2 fixation, dry matter production, and N yield. □

Effect of sesbania and azolla on rice grain and straw yields

M. Kalidurai and S. Kannaiyan, Biotechnology Unit, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

We evaluated *Sesbania rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, and *Azolla microphylla* as N sources for rice during 1987-88 dry (Jun-Sep) and wet (Oct-Feb) seasons. The field had moderately drained clay soil (pH 8.2, EC 0.3 dS/m, 288 kg N/ha, 15 kg P/ha, and 526 kg /ha). CO 43 was planted in 1-m² plots. Fresh biomass of *S. rostrata*, *S. aculeata*, and *Azolla microphylla* at 20 t/ha with N content 3.7%, 2.9%, and 2.5% in the dry season and 3.64%, 3.05%, and 2.37% in the wet season, respectively, were incorporated 2 d before planting and allowed to decompose. Prilled

Effect of green manure on rice grain and straw yields. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Straw yield (t/ha)	
	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season
Control	2.3	2.8	6.2	6.5
Prilled urea				
60 kg N/ha	2.8	3.2	6.4	6.8
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. rostrata</i>	5.7	6.0	14.0	14.1
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. aculeata</i>	4.4	4.7	12.6	12.8
60 kg N/ha + <i>A. microphylla</i>	3.5	4.0	6.8	7.4
100 kg N/ha	3.7	3.9	7.0	7.3
Neem-coated urea				
60 kg N/ha	3.2	3.7	7.0	7.0
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. rostrata</i>	5.9	6.2	14.4	15.1
60 kg N/ha + <i>S. aculeata</i>	5.0	5.1	13.2	14.3
60 kg N/ha + <i>A. microphylla</i>	3.9	4.5	8.3	9.0
100 kg N/ha	3.9	4.3	8.8	8.8
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.4	0.7	0.9	0.3

urea (PU) and neem-coated prilled urea (NCU) were applied at 60 and 100 kg N/ha, in a random block design with three replications. K and P (50 kg/ha) were basally applied.

S. rostrata and *S. aculeata* with 60 kg N/ha significantly increased grain and straw yields (see table). In all treatments, NCU enhanced yields more than did PU alone. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Potential antagonist of rice sheath rot (ShR) pathogen

R. Viswanathan and P. Narayanasamy, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641 003, India

We studied the antagonistic potential of some phylloplane fungal and bacterial isolates on the growth of rice pathogens *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara, *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, and *Sarocladium oryzae* Sawada.

Phylloplane isolates of bacteria and fungi obtained from leaf samples taken from healthy plants of seven rice varieties are presented in the table. To test interaction with fungal isolates, the

pathogen and the test organism were placed 4 cm apart on potato-dextrose agar medium in petri plates. To test interaction with bacterial isolates, the pathogen was placed at one end of the

plate and allowed to grow for 3 to 4 d, then the test bacterium was streaked 4 cm from the growing edge of the pathogen colony.

Fungal isolate *Bipolaris zeicola* (Stout) Shoem obtained from IR20 at tillering inhibited mycelial growth of

Population of phylloplane microorganisms in different rice varieties. Coimbatore, India.

Rice variety	Colony-forming units ^a (no./g leaf)			
	Tillering phase		Late boot leaf stage	
	Bacteria × 10 ³	Fungi × 10 ²	Bacteria × 10 ³	Fungi × 10 ²
IR20	24.33	11.33	35.67	12.00
IR50	25.41	11.67	35.67	11.67
CO 43	25.33	11.67	36.00	12.00
ASD16	23.33	12.00	35.00	12.33
IR64	24.67	11.67	35.33	12.33
IR70	24.33	11.33	36.00	13.00
Ponni	25.67	12.60	36.33	13.67

^a Mean of 3 replications.